
A QUALITY MODEL FOR DATA LAKES AND DATA LAKEHOUSES

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1 Introduction

1.1 Quality Models

While standards like ISO/IEC 9126 and its successor ISO/IEC 25010 have provided a structured foundation for assessing software quality based on product-oriented attributes, recent efforts suggest that this perspective is no longer sufficient to capture the complexity of modern software systems and contexts. A relevant reference on this regarding is the *Guide to the Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK)* that represents a globally recognized effort to codify the generally accepted knowledge in software engineering. Now in its fourth version, SWEBOK is the result of decades of consensus-building among researchers, educators, and practitioners, and serves as a foundational reference for curricula design, professional certification, and process standards across Information Technologies disciplines [1].

Given its broad acceptance and technical authority, SWEBOK offers a privileged vantage point from which to examine the concept of software quality. In particular, the guide provides structured insight into how software quality is defined, managed, and evaluated across the lifecycle of software systems. This makes it an essential source for analyzing the rationale and components of quality models for software-related process, product and services.

A software quality model serves to organize the diverse meanings and targets of quality in engineering practice. The *SWEBOK Guide* emphasizes that software quality is not a monolithic concept, but rather a multifaceted one that encompasses product attributes, process characteristics, and organizational behaviors. A quality model allows these aspects to be systematically represented, making it possible to communicate expectations, align practices, and evaluate outcomes throughout the software life cycle [2].

The primary purpose of a software quality model is to support stakeholder alignment and engineering traceability. According to *SWEBOK*, defining what quality means for a software product is essential to achieving stakeholder agreement and guiding engineering decisions. The guide notes that “agreeing on what constitutes software quality for all stakeholders and communicating that agreement to software engineers requires that the many aspects of quality be formally defined and communicated” [2]. In this sense, a quality model provides not only a taxonomy of attributes but also a shared vocabulary and reference point across project roles and phases.

A comprehensive model of software quality integrates characteristics, practices, and perspectives. *SWEBOK* outlines that software quality knowledge is distributed across multiple views: product, process, and work products [3]. This triadic view enables a richer understanding of how quality emerges and can be assured. In its structure, a quality model often includes: (1) fundamental concepts and definitions; (2) processes for managing and assuring quality; (3) tools for measurement and control; and (4) broader considerations such as culture, ethics, and cost of quality. This layered structure ensures that both measurable attributes and contextual factors are taken into account when evaluating or improving software quality—during the development life cycle and also afterward, not only in terms of maintenance and adaptation to future needs, but in how the system continues to fulfill its evolving role and meaning for its stakeholders.

Several scholars support this broader point of view of quality concerns adding different aspects beyond technical attributes. For example, Palomares et al. propose the inclusion of non-technical quality characteristics derived from real-world procurement practices, such as supplier structure, business constraints, and project-specific relationships [4]. Their extensions introduces novel categories—such as *Supplier*, *Business*, *Product*, and *Project*—and decomposes them into sub-characteristics, offering a descriptive vocabulary for evaluating software solutions in procurement

contexts. Similarly, Saha and Srivastava emphasize the importance of data quality management in the context of big data systems, introducing veracity as a critical dimension alongside volume, velocity, and variety [5]. They argue that data quality should encompass consistency, accuracy, and completeness, but also the capacity to discover and enforce semantic integrity in highly heterogeneous and dynamic data environments.

However, building a holistic quality model is not only about adding non-recognized aspects. It also requires confronting foundational issues related to the conceptual coherence and internal structure of the models themselves. Moreover, concerns about conceptual alignment and coherence across quality models reveal that inconsistencies in definitions and overlapping constructs may obscure a clear understanding of what “quality” means in different domains, thus prompting efforts to systematize and formalize model comparison [6]. These issues suggest that the challenge is not only what dimensions are included, but also how these dimensions are articulated and represented. In this regard, it becomes necessary to shift attention from the object-level definition of quality to a meta-level analysis of the quality of the quality models themselves.

This perspective is formalized in the SEQUAL framework developed by Krogstie and collaborators, which proposes a semiotic foundation for evaluating models. SEQUAL distinguishes multiple facets of model quality—syntactic, semantic, pragmatic, and social—each oriented toward different aspects of model use and interpretation. Beyond formal correctness, it emphasizes the extent to which a model captures relevant domain knowledge (semantic quality), is interpretable and usable by its audience (pragmatic quality), and is accepted and agreed upon among stakeholders (social quality)

. These criteria are particularly pertinent when models serve not only descriptive but also normative functions, as in the case of quality models meant to guide software development or acquisition decisions.

Building on this, some authors have attempted to operationalize these semiotic dimensions to evaluate quality models in practice. For instance, Cares et al. propose a method to assess quality models by mapping their structure and content onto simplified SEQUAL criteria—semantic, pragmatic, and social quality—and identifying sources of ambiguity or misalignment in their formulation.

Adopting this reflective stance reveals that improving quality models is not only a matter of expansion but also of critical modeling discipline—a discipline that examines how quality is conceptualized, communicated, and institutionally embedded.

1.2 Quality in the Data Management Body of Knowledge

Data quality is a central concept in data management. Organizations manage their data to ensure it meets business needs. If the data cannot be relied upon, the effort to collect, store, secure, and enable access to it is wasted¹.

The dimension of data quality encompasses attributes related to the reliability, precision, completeness, relevance, timeliness, consistency, and integrity of data. These attributes are essential for ensuring that data is useful and trustworthy for business decisions and strategic initiatives².

Metadata quality includes attributes such as the precision, completeness, relevance, timeliness, consistency, and integrity of metadata. Metadata describes what data an organization has, what it represents, how it is classified, where it came from, how it moves within the organization, how it evolves through use, who can and cannot use it, and whether it is of high quality³.

Data management process quality involves attributes related to strategic planning, collaboration between business and IT, effective project execution, process efficiency, and process effectiveness. These attributes ensure that data management processes are well-designed and executed to meet organizational goals⁴.

¹Ensuring that data is of high quality is central to data management. Organizations manage their data because they want to use it. If they cannot rely on it to meet business needs, then the effort to collect, store, secure, and enable access to it is wasted. (DAMA-DMBOK, p. 17)

²Most uses of data involve learning from it in order to apply that learning and create value. Examples include understanding customer habits in order to improve a product or service and assessing organizational performance or market trends in order to develop a better business strategy, etc. Poor quality data will have a negative impact on these decisions. (DAMA-DMBOK, p. 18)

³Metadata describes what data an organization has, what it represents, how it is classified, where it came from, how it moves within the organization, how it evolves through use, who can and cannot use it, and whether it is of high quality. (DAMA-DMBOK, p. 20)

⁴Planning for better data requires a strategic approach to architecture, modeling, and other design functions. It also depends on strategic collaboration between business and IT leadership. And, of course, it depends on the ability to execute effectively on individual projects. (DAMA-DMBOK, p. 21)

The quality of tools and techniques used in data management includes attributes such as the precision, completeness, relevance, timeliness, consistency, and integrity of these tools and techniques. Examples of tools include data profiling tools, data querying tools, modeling and ETL tools, data quality rule templates, and metadata repositories⁵.

Data governance quality encompasses attributes related to the clarity, effectiveness, consistency, transparency, and accountability of data governance policies. These attributes ensure that data governance practices are well-defined and enforced within the organization⁶.

Data security quality includes attributes such as confidentiality, integrity, availability, protection against breaches, and access control. These attributes ensure that data is protected from unauthorized access and misuse⁷.

Ethical data handling quality involves attributes such as transparency, accountability, justice, beneficence, and respect for persons. These attributes ensure that data is handled in an ethical manner, respecting the rights and dignity of individuals⁸.

Data architecture quality includes attributes related to alignment with organizational strategy, clarity of data requirements, effectiveness of data designs, consistency, and flexibility of the architecture. These attributes ensure that the data architecture supports the organization's goals and enables effective data management⁹.

1.3 Total Quality Management and IT-Specific Quality Frameworks

This section analyses Total Quality Management (TQM) and its relationship to IT-specific quality frameworks (such as ITIL, COBIT, and CMMI-SVC) within the relatively recent literature. The selected articles explicitly include arguments, conceptual alignments, or critiques that link general quality management models to the domain of IT service and product quality.

To understand how different quality frameworks are related to TQM, it's important to specify TQM as a reference architecture, or reference framework who acts like the umbrella providing cultural and strategic basis for their operational excellence (ref).

IT-Specific quality frameworks are, specific implementations of some, or all TQM principles, looking for transform their principles in concrete, auditable, metrics or maturity levels(ref) .

With this in consideration, the diferent frameworks represent their principles in this different ways:

- ITIL: ITIL takes the Kaizen Principle, who is defined by continual improvement, named as Service Value System, who is composed of several elements, being one of them the Continual Improvement Model (ref). ITIL's continual Improvement Model as an iterative approach consider seven logical steps, who is closely aligned with Plan-Do-Check-Act cycle, one of the pillars of TQM.
 - What is the Vision?
 - Where are we Now?
 - Where do we want to be?
 - How do we get there?
 - Take Action!
 - Did we get there?
 - How do we keep the momentum going?

⁵Data profiling tools, data querying tools, modeling and ETL tools, data quality rule templates, metadata repositories. (DAMA-DMBOK, p. 23)

⁶Data Governance is a vital tool for ensuring these principles are considered in deciding who can do what with which data and under what circumstances processing is appropriate or necessary. The ethical impacts and risks of data processing on all stakeholders must be considered by practitioners, and managed in a similar manner to data quality. (DAMA-DMBOK, p. 25)

⁷Data Security ensures that data privacy and confidentiality are maintained, that data is not breached, and that data is accessed appropriately. (DAMA-DMBOK, p. 27)

⁸The ethical principle of 'do not harm' has a long history in medical ethics, but also has clear application in the context of data and information management. Ethical data and information practitioners should identify stakeholders and consider the outcomes of data processing and work to maximize benefit and minimize risk of harm caused by the processes designed. (DAMA-DMBOK, p. 29)

⁹Data Architecture defines the blueprint for managing data assets by aligning with organizational strategy to establish strategic data requirements and designs to meet these requirements. (DAMA-DMBOK, p. 31)

- COBIT: it's defined as Control Objectives for Business and Related Technology, looking for ensure effective an efficient use of IT to achieve business objectives. ITIL consider three stages defined by Monitor, Evaluate and Assess (MEA).
 - MEA01 (Manage performance and conformance monitoring)
 - MEA02 (Manage the internal control system)
 - MEA03 (Manage compliance with external requirements)
- CMMI-SVC: Capability Maturity Model Integration provides organizations with elements for effective processes (cita3), CMMI in services (SVC) applies to services management in TI. This framework takes the umbrella of TQM an defines an structured path using their five leves of maturity:
 - Level 1, Initial, with unpredictable processes, Dependency of individuals and low levels of standarization.
 - Level 2 (Managed): Based on processes being planned, executed, and monitored.²³ This reflects the start of the TQM commitment to process management and control.²
 - Level 3 (Defined): Processes are standardized across the entire organization.²² This translates TQM's Integrated System 2 principle into a formal organizational asset.
 - Level 4 (Quantitatively Managed): Process performance is measured and managed with data.²² This level is the direct manifestation of TQM's Fact-Based Decision Making principle.²
 - Level 5 (Optimizing): Processes are subject to continual improvement driven by innovation and data analysis.²² This is the culmination of TQM's Kaizen concept.²

Table 1 resumes the relationship between TQM and TI Governance and quality management frameworks

Table 1: Relationship and application of TQM principles in governance and IT management

Central principle of TQM	ITIL (Services and management)	COBIT (IT control & governance)	CMMI-SVC (Process Maturity)
Client focus	Value creation for clients [1], using value focus.[2]	IT aligned with business goals[4]	beliefs in organization capacity to achieve requirements.[5, 6]
Continous improvement (Kaizen)	operative application of PDCA in seven steps[7, 8]	MEA Domine[9], measuring performance, and feeds estrategic aligement.[3]	Level 5 based on continuous improvement guided by data analysis.[10]
Prevention vs. Inspection	Problem management focus, looking for prevention [11]	MEA02 (Manage internal control system)[9]	Process and products quality assesment (PPQA) [12]
Fact-Based Decision Making	KPIs and service metrics to validate processes[8]	MEA requires performance and conformity measurement [3]	Level 5 requires data driven processes and performance measurement .[10]
Integrated system & standarization	Service Value System integrating all components to create value.	"Integrator" as a goverment structure generator, aligning frameworks	Level three demands standarized process, adapted to organizational actives[10, 5]

1.4 Data Lakes

The concept of data lake was first introduced by James Dixon, the Chief Technology Officer of Pentaho, in 2010 as a solution to overcome limitations of data marts, which are business-specific subsets of data warehouses that allow only a limited set of questions to be answered [7, 8, 9]. Dixon envisioned a data lake as "a large storage system for raw, heterogeneous data, fed by multiple data sources, and that allows users to explore, extract and analyze the data" [7]. In Dixon's original analogy, "whilst a data warehouse seems to be a bottle of water cleaned and ready for consumption, then 'Data Lake' is considered as a whole lake of data in a more natural state". In this study, we consider that a data lake is a centralized repository that stores raw, structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data at scale, enabling flexible processing and analysis for diverse and evolving decision-making needs. We arrived at this understanding by

Figure 1: Data Lake definition and utilities for Big Data management.

reviewing various definitions. For example, Zagan and Danubianu [10] refer to structured and unstructured data, but it also seems necessary to include semi-structured data, such as data formatted using JSON or XML.

Data lakes possess several distinct characteristics that differentiate them from traditional data storage systems:

- Raw Data Storage, allowing organizations to capture data in its natural state [11].
- Schema-on-Read Approach, where data structure is not defined until the data is needed[12].
- Support for All Data Types, structured, semi-structured and unstructured data from various sources [13].
- Scalability allowing to handle massive volumes of data from multiple sources[7].
- Centralized Repository bringing all data into a single system for further analysis[14].
- Cost-Effective Storage using for example HADOOP Distributed File Systems or object storage solutions [12].
- Metadata Management using catalogs that enforce data quality and support data governance [7].
- Flexibility for New Data Formats, allowing organizations to store different datasets from various sources [15].
- Support for Advanced analytics, focused in real-time analytics and machine learning techniques [16].

The balance between harnessing large volumes of data and protecting individual privacy has become a central challenge in the Big Data era. Regulations such as the EU’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) seek to safeguard privacy, but their implementation in Big Data environments is complex [17]. In Big Data systems with large volumes of heterogeneous information, it is difficult to track and control the entire data lifecycle, which makes complying with all GDPR requirements still “a real challenge” in various areas, from industrial organizations to healthcare sectors [17, 18, 7].

To support this cycle, the concept of the Data Lake becomes relevant in Big Data systems, aiming to maintain information in its various forms across different layers. This facilitates traceability and data lifecycle management [19], through the use of components such as metadata to support these processes [20]. Figure 1 summarizes the main features and benefits of the Data Lake in data lifecycle management.

Although the Data Lake concept has been accepted and addressed, there are no standards in its modeling or the components that ensure system or model quality, as Data Lake solutions tend to be tailored to the specific problem addressed [21].

Quality is a criterion defined in different ways depending on perspective. In software, in particular, quality is based on customer satisfaction rather than structure, and it should focus on how well the software helps customers accomplish their tasks [22]. This inherently suggests that the quality of a system is associated with the client’s needs, allowing for the existence of systems of the same type that, despite having different levels of quality, effectively fulfill their intended purposes. Criteria for measuring quality as a general concept exist across various domains—from system construction quality to data quality [23, 24, 25, 26]—and include best practice recommendations already considered standard in data management processes [27].

To implement these different quality criteria, quality models are employed. A data quality model is defined as a proven set of activities aimed at improving data quality in various contexts and initial conditions [28]. These models, due to how quality criteria are defined, measure the level of system quality in an “agnostic” manner. They do not seek to make value judgments but rather provide comparisons based on the ontological distances between the model and the system being evaluated, which, ideally, is isomorphic [29]. From a business perspective, measuring software quality reduces costs, improves development and maintenance productivity, which translates into higher-value outcomes, and enhances software quality overall [30]. Although quality measurement systems exist, no data lake quality models are currently presented in the literature. The absence of a reference framework for evaluating different data lake systems can lead to inconsistent perceptions and the implementation of systems that either do not meet user needs [31] or deviate significantly from the intended system model [29].

This paper presents guidelines for the components to be considered in a comprehensive quality model for evaluating data lake systems, along with a first version of the measurement model, detailing its dimensions and sub-dimensions. The paper follows the structure of related works, then presents the quality components to be considered, followed by the proposed model, and concludes with a discussion of the model, its components, and its implications.

2 Related Works

Several approaches have been proposed in the literature to address data quality management, which can be grouped into four main categories: maturity assessment models, process-oriented models, corporate frameworks, and specialized models. In the area of maturity models, Belghith et al. [32] develops a comparative metamodel that enables the analysis of different models based on structural and contextual criteria. Caballero et al. [33] presents a data quality model inspired by the levels of the CMMI model, emphasizing continuous improvement. Kim and Lee [34], on the other hand, proposes a reference model aligned with standards such as SPICE and ISO 8000-150, facilitating its integration with existing regulatory frameworks. From a corporate perspective, Otto and Österle [35] introduces a data quality model that organizes its components into six design areas, ranging from organizational strategy to technological architecture.

On the other hand, from the perspective of data lake quality, Brous et al. [36] proposes a governance framework incorporating both automated and manual auditing tools for enterprise environments. Farid et al. [37] develops CLAMS, a system designed to discover and enforce integrity constraints on large volumes of heterogeneous data. Redyuk et al. [38] applies machine learning-based novelty detection to validate dynamic data without relying on predefined rules. Meanwhile, Diamantini et al. [39], Eder and Shekhovtsov [40] presents approaches centered on metadata management, emphasizing metrics such as completeness, coverage, and consistency. Although these proposals are varied and promising, many exhibit limitations, such as a lack of empirical validation, restricted applicability to specific domains, or a still-conceptual nature.

3 Quality components

To determine which quality components should be addressed, it is essential to first understand that, when considering the data lake as a holistic system, several layers must be taken into account. These typically include data sources, ingestion processes, transformed data storage [19], visualization systems or similar components (particularly in data lakehouse architectures), and a layer associated with metadata management. Based on these four areas, several quality components must be considered, including:

- Data Governance
- Organizational Quality
- Data Quality
- Model Quality
- Metamodel Quality
- Procedure Quality
- Metadata Quality

3.1 Organizational Quality

La calidad de la organización se encuentra intrínsecamente asociado a la gestión de los sistemas de software, por lo cual influye de manera holística en los Datalakes. * Idea de establecer ISO2500, ISO 27000, ITIL de cara a estándares de calidad organizacional. * Indicadores desde aquí

Teamwork quality and project success in software development: A survey of agile development teams.

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3.2 Data governance

Data governance refers to the formal management systems that oversee an organization’s data assets throughout their lifecycle. While there is no single standardized definition, several prominent organizations and scholars have provided complementary perspectives. The Data Governance Institute defines it as ”a system of decision rights and accountabilities for information-related processes, executed according to agreed-upon models which describe who can take what actions with what information, and when, under what circumstances, using what methods” (Al-Ruithe et al., 2018).

Intrinsic Quality: Quality that data possesses in its own right

Accuracy/Free-of-Error: The extent to which data is correct and reliable Objectivity: The degree to which data is unbiased and impartial Believability: The extent to which data is regarded as true and credible Reputation: The extent to which data is highly regarded in terms of source or content

3.3 Data Quality

The term “data” lacks a universally accepted definition, but it is generally understood as a representation of facts, concepts, or instructions in a formalized manner, suitable for communication, interpretation, or processing. Its quality can be determined by the following subcategories [41].

- Accuracy: Degree to which the data reflect reality.
- Completeness: Absence of missing data.
- Consistency: Absence of contradictions within the dataset.
- Timeliness (currency): The data are up to date and relevant.
- Accessibility: Ease of access to the data for users.
- Representation: Clarity and appropriate formatting of the data.
- Relevance: Suitability of the data for the specific context or task.
- Reliability and provenance: Trust in the source and traceability of the origin of the data.

To measure data quality, the standards defined by the Data Management Body of Knowledge (DMBOK) are used. This establishes the criteria for validating data quality, which are: consistency, completeness, validity, accessibility, traceability and accuracy. All these components are fundamental to ensure data quality, which should be the core of the Data Lake system.

3.4 Model quality

A quality model provides a conceptual framework for identifying, organizing, and evaluating the different aspects that make up quality in a specific context, such as software, services, education, or manufacturing. These models help establish clear criteria for the evaluation, comparison, and continuous improvement of quality. [? ? ?] As defined by DAMA-DMBOK, models can be evaluated in the following areas [27, 42]:

- Requirements capture
- Model completeness
- Alignment with schema
- Structural soundness
- Consistency with business model

3.5 Metamodel quality

A metamodel in software is a structure that defines the rules, concepts, and relationships of a modeling language, serving as a “model of models.” Its quality is essential, as it directly affects the usefulness and accuracy of the models

and transformations that are based on it. Evaluating the quality of a metamodel requires specific parameters and metrics[43, 44] taking for example:

- Mantenibility
- Reutilization
- Undersandability

3.6 Procedural quality

Software procedures are sets of structured steps or activities that guide the development, operation, maintenance, and management of software systems [? ?]. In this case, since the data lake is considered as a holistic system, we seek to consider the quality components associated with the processes [24, 23], which define:

- Process definition.
- Value streams.
- Continous improvement.
- End-to-end vision.

3.7 Metadata Quality

Un metamodelo en software es una estructura que define las reglas, conceptos y relaciones de un lenguaje de modelado, sirviendo como “modelo de modelos”. Su calidad es fundamental, ya que impacta directamente en la utilidad y precisión de los modelos y transformaciones que se basan en él [27]. Metadata should be, in the first place, planned and managed as its own product, given the value it generates.

- Degree to which the metadata contains all the necessary information.
- Accuracy of the information recorded in the metadata.
- Consistency in the representation of data throughout the system.
- Ease with which users can access and use the metadata
- Scope and breadth of the information described by the metadata
- Updating and timeliness of the metadata
- Compliance with standards or expectations defined by the community or domain
- Information about the origin and history of the metadata
- Confidence in the truthfulness and stability of the metadata

4 Model & discussion

Figure 2 presents a summary of the parameters defined in the previous section, aiming to group and subcategorize them based on a common model.

Figure 2: Initial data lake quality model. Visual figure made in Napkin

The model in 2 considers that not all quality criteria are applicable to all components of a Data Lake, and not all sub-criteria are applicable either, for example when talking about completeness, it is a criterion that cannot be applied to the raw data source, since the data in its environment may not exist complete, and its components are “repaired” in subsequent processes. Therefore, within the data source stage, only valid and accessible data are considered to be valid and accessible, in order to start the ingestion processes.

The ingestion and storage processes consider more complete data quality components, since by definition a data lake must be traceable in its processes and in the transformation of its data [45, 19], and it is also supported by quality criteria of the procedures, mainly components of value flows and point-to-point vision, that is, considering the processes as part of a macro-process that is the system itself [46].

Metadata components must inherently consider all metadata quality components, but, in addition to the obvious, end-to-end vision components of procedural quality must be considered, because the correct management of metadata prevents the generation of a data swamp, i.e. a data lake that is not capable of generating value, so that the processes associated with the metadata are validated becomes crucial for the organization [47, 48].

Another important component to consider is the quality components of the system at a holistic level, where the characteristics associated with the model, such as completeness or consistency with the organization become fundamental components [49, 50]. In addition to criteria associated with the procedures, with special emphasis on the definition of processes, and the continuous improvement of the system, which will inherently depend on all the other quality criteria being considered.

5 Conclusion

This work presents a first iteration of a data quality model specifically designed for data lakes. Initially, a comprehensive review of the literature was conducted, followed by an evaluation of the various quality dimensions to be considered. These dimensions ultimately informed the development of the initial version of the proposed data lake quality model.

The main contribution of this model lies in its ability to establish a set of guidelines for assessing the quality status of different data lake implementations. Rather than aiming to identify or rank the “best” data lake, the model seeks to indicate quality levels in a way that facilitates the comparison between the ontological structure of a data lake and the actual needs of the organization. This comparison enables organizations to minimize the ontological gap and work towards achieving a data lake that is isomorphic to the realities and requirements of the organization.

Future work, which is already underway, involves the development of a system that automatically measures the degree to which a data lake system aligns with organizational needs, based on the proposed quality model. This system is expected to identify areas for improvement and provide organizations with actionable insights into quality enhancement opportunities deemed relevant to their specific context.

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